
**SCHEMES AND PROGRAMS FOR AGRICULTURE
DEVELOPMENT AND IT'S IMPACT**

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Abstract:

Agricultural policy of India is generally designed by the government to raise agricultural production and productivity and also to upgrade the level of income and standard of farmers within a definite time frame. Agriculture is one of the important backbones of Indian economy. Agriculture has special significance for low income, poor and vulnerable sections of rural society. Agricultural Growth rate of Agricultural development and crop production and productivity which will strengthen the economic status of the farmers and uplift their life-style. The policies were initially focused on the expansion of cultivated area introduction of land reforms, community development, minimum support prices, public storage, procurement and distribution of food grains, trade protection measures and restructuring of rural credit in situation. Objective of my research study are to the important of the agricultural scheme and policy; to study the organisations of central govt. Agricultural scheme and policy; to study the organisations of Maharashtra govt. Agricultural scheme and policy; to study the agricultural problems in India; to study the schemes for development of Agricultural and farmers, welfare. Present research study will depend upon secondary dada. Secondary data collection from agricultural schemes and policy and farmers welfare.

Key word: Welfare, Policy, Schemes, Impact, Production.

Introduction:

Agriculture is one of the important backbones of Indian economy. Agriculture has special significance for low income, poor and vulnerable sections of rural society. India's agriculture policy stabs to ensure that agricultural is profitable and farm prices are stable through assured minimum support prices (MSP) public distribution system (PDS).

Agricultural policy of India is generally designed by the government to raise agricultural production and productivity and also to upgrade the level of income and standard of farmers within a definite time frame. This policy is formulated for all rounds and evolution of Agricultural Policies has remained a highly structured sector in India with government organizations and parastatals

exercising a pervasive influence over it. These regulatory controls are imposed by both central and state government. The main policy measures in the agriculture sector were adopted in the mid 1960.

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On 28 July 2000 the NDA Govt. Made public a National Agriculture policy envisaging over 4 percent annual growth through efficient use of resources and technology and increased private investment while emphasizing on price protection to farmers in the WTO regime.

Agricultural Growth rate of Agricultural development and crop production and productivity which will strengthen the economic status of the farmers and uplift their life-style.

Objectives of the study:

- 1) To study the important of the agricultural scheme and policy.
- 2) To study the organisations of central govt. Agricultural scheme and policy.

- 3) To study the organisations of Maharashtra govt. Agricultural scheme and policy.
- 4) To study the agricultural problems in India.
- 5) To study the schemes for development of Agricultural and farmers, welfare.
- 6) To give some conclusion.

Research Methodology:

The present study studied by Agricultural schemes and policies in India. This study is based on secondary data. The secondary data have been collected from various sources such as published and unpublished books, website.

The Govt. Agriculture schemes:

1) Launch of Pradhan Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana:

Farming has become an undoable sector. Farmers are always unsure of the yield they'll reap, but strive to draw the maximum benefits out of their investments and effort often farmers might be at the receiving end, with natural calamities like drought and floods affecting their yield adversely. To resolve the problem of unpredictable nature of farming and prevent farmer suicides in the country, the Government launched PM Mantri Fasal Bima Yojana in early 2016. It's a crop insurance policy with relaxed premium

rates on the principal sum insured for farmers. Implemented with a budget of Rs. 17600 crore, this scheme will provide financial support to farmers and cover for their losses. This initiative is expected to go on floors from the next kharif season of farming that is from June 2016.

2) After green, white, golden, it's time for blue:

The cabinet committee on economic Affairs (CCEA) has approved Blue Revolution in India. It's an integrated scheme designed to increase the productivity and profitability from aquaculture and fisheries inductive of both inland and marine. With a budget of Rs. 3000 offered by government for the next five year. The scheme aim to maintain an annual growth rate of six to eight percent of the agriculture and allied sector.

3) Government to invest Rs. 221 crore to improve milk productivity:

India boasts of being the largest producer of milk in the world with an annual output of 130 million tonnes. However, with milk producing animal population of more than 118 million, the milk yields per animal is very low. To meet the steadily Dairy Development Board (NDDB) has announced 42 dairy project, under a budget of 221 crore. These projects shall focus on improving the milk productivity of major milk producing state

like Uttar Pradesh, Maharashtra, Karnataka, Tamil Nadu and the likes.

4) Energy-efficient irrigation to be implemented:

A report says that in India more than two-thirds of the arable area lacks proper irrigational facilities. Taking note of this, Power Minister Piyush Goyal said that the government is planning on investing Rs. 75000 crore to provide energy efficient irrigational facilities to farmer, over the next three to four years. Under this scheme close to 30 million energy saving pump sets would be given to farmers and cost would be recovered via savings in the electricity consumed. This would result in about 46 billion KWh of power being saved and creation of 20 lakh jobs.

5) Launch of Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana:

The government has launched Paramparagat Krishi Vikas Yojana in order to address the critical importance of soil and water for improving agricultural production. The government would support and improve the organic farming practices prevalent in India following, at least 50 farmers would form a group having 50 acres of land to implement organic farming. The government aim to cover 10,000 clusters and five lakh hectares of arable land under organic farming within three years.

Recently, the government has been active in investing in agricultural infrastructure such as irrigational facilities, mechanised farming and warehousing. The growing use of genetically modified crop will also improve the sector's contribution look promising, in what way are they going to affect the current scenario is something interesting to watch out for.

6) Soil Health Card Scheme:

Launched in 2015 the scheme has been introduced to assist state Governments to issue soil health cards to all farmers in the country. The soil health cards provide information to farmers on nutrient status of their soil along with recommendation on appropriate dosage of nutrients to be appropriate dosage of nutrients to be applied for improving soil health and its fertility.

7) National Mission for Sustainable Agriculture (NMSA):

NMSA is one of the eight Mission under National Action Plan on Climate Change (NMSA). It aims at promoting Sustainable Agriculture through climate change adaptation measures, enhancing agriculture productivity especially in rainfed areas focusing on integrated farming, soil health management, and synergizing resource conservation.

NMSA as a programmatic intervention caters to Mission Deliverables that focuses mainly on conservation

agriculture to mark farm sector more productive sustainable, remunerative and climate resilient by promoting location specific integrated/composite farming system. Schemes under NMSA in rainfed area development, soil health management, sub mission on agro forestry, paramparagat krishi vikas yojana, soil and land use survey of India, national rain fed area authority, mission organic value chain development in north eastern region, national centre of organic farming, central fertilizer quality control and training.

8) Neem Coated Urea (NCU):

This scheme is initiated to regulate use of urea, enhance availability of nitrogen to the crop and reduce cost of fertilizer application. NCU slows down the release of fertilizer and makes it available to the crop in an effective manner. The entire quantity of domestically manufactured and imported urea is now neem coated. It reduces the cost of cultivation and improves soil health management.

9) Pradhan Mantri Krishi Sinchai Yojana (PMKSY):

It was launched on July 2015 with motto of 'Har Khet Ko Paani' for providing end to end solution in irrigation supply chain, viz. Water sources, distribution network and farm level application.

PMKSY not only focuses on creating sources for assured irrigation, but also creating protective irrigation, but also creating protective irrigation by harnessing rain water at micro level through 'Jal Sanchay' and 'Jal Sanchan'.

Micro irrigation is to be popularised to ensure 'Per drop- More crop'. PMKSY adopts States level planning and projectised execution that allows States to draw up their own irrigation development based on District Irrigation Plans and States Irrigation Plans.

10) Livestock Insurance Scheme:

It aim to provide protection mechanism to the farmers and cattle rearers against any eventual loss of animal due to death. The scheme also demonstrates the benefit of the insurance of livestock to the people and popularizes it with the ultimate goal of attaining qualitative improvement in livestock and their products.

11) Micro Irrigation Fund (MIF):

A dedicated MIF created with NABARD has been approved with an initial corpus of Rs. 5000 crore for encouraging public and private investments in Micro irrigation. The main objective of the fund is to facilitate the States in mobilizing the resources for expanding coverage of Micro Irrigation.

MIF would not only facilitate States in incentivizing and mobilizing

resources for achieving the target envisaged under PMKSY-PDMC but also in bringing additional coverage through special and innovative initiatives by state government.

An advisory committee has been set up to provide policy direction and ensure effective planning. Coordination and monitoring of the micro irrigation fund.

Maharashtra Government Schemes:

- 1) Soil Health, Soil Conservation and fertilisers.
- 2) Seeds.
- 3) Irrigation.
- 4) Training and Extension for farmers.
- 5) Machinery and Technology.
- 6) Agriculture Credit.
- 7) Agricultural Insurance.
- 8) Plant protection.
- 9) Horticulture.
- 10) Agricultural Marketing.

Crop related policies and schemes:

- 1) Krishi Unnati Yojana.
- 2) Rashtriya Krishi Vikas Yojana.
- 3) Pradhanmantri Krishi Sinchan Yojana.
- 4) Ground Water Irrigation Scheme.
- 5) Pradhanmantri Kisan Sampada Yojana.
- 6) Pradhan Mantra Annadata Sanrakshan Abhiyan.

- 7) Jute Development Schemes.
- 8) Schemes On Seeds.

Impact:

Some of the major problems and their possible solutions have been discussed as follows. Indian agriculture is plagued by several impacts; some of them are natural and some others are manmade.

- 1) Seeds.
- 2) Manures, fertilizers and biocides.
- 3) Irrigation.
- 4) Lack of mechanisation.
- 5) Soil reason.
- 6) Agricultural marketing.
- 7) Inadequate storage facilities.
- 8) Inadequate transport.
- 9) Security of capital.

Schemes for development of agriculture and farmers welfare:

The department of agriculture and cooperation was earlier implementing 51 schemes for development of agriculture and welfare of farmers in the country. These schemes have recently been restructured into 5 centrally sponsored missions, 5 central sector schemes and 1 state plan scheme as given below.

Centrally sponsored missions:

- 1) National food security mission (NFSM)
- 2) National mission on sustainable agriculture (NMSA)
- 3) National mission on oilseeds and oil palm (NMOOP)
- 4) National mission and technology (NMAET)
- 5) Mission of integrated development of horticulture (MIDH)

Conclusion:

Finally researcher concludes the agricultural scheme and policy then development of agricultural sector and farmer's welfare. Raising the productivity of inputs and modernizing agricultural sector. Agricultural research and training. Protecting the interest of underprivileged agriculturalists. Checking environmental degradation.

References:

1. yourstory.com
2. yourarticlelibrary.com
3. Pib.nic.in
4. Agricoop.gov.in
5. Kisansuvidha.com
6. <https://en.m.wikipedia.org>
7. Upageripardarsdarshi.gov.in